

Integrated dynamical thermal compensation techniques for Advanced Virgo

I. Nardecchia^{1,2}, L. Aiello^{1,2}, E. Cesarini², D. Lumaca^{1,2}, V. Fafone^{1,2},
R. Maggiore^{1,2}, M. Lorenzini^{1,2}, Y. Minenkov², A. Rocchi²

¹ Dipartimento di Fisica, Via della Ricerca Scientifica, Univ. of Roma Tor Vergata, 00133 Rome, Italy

² INFN Roma Tor Vergata, Via della Ricerca Scientifica, 00133 Rome, Italy

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Abstract

The path of the Advanced Virgo gravitational-wave interferometer toward its design sensitivity features a substantial increase of the laser beam power with respect to the first generation detectors. The absorption of the laser power by the mirrors causes a thermal expansion of the optics itself along the optical axis (thermo-elastic effect) and an increase of the optical path length of the light inside the cavities due to the refractive index variations (thermo-refractive effect commonly called thermal lensing). These two physical processes have two main consequences on the interferometer (ITF) optical configuration: they change the radius of curvature of the high reflectivity (HR) surface of the mirror, and generate a thermal lens in the bulk of the optics due to the heat transfer from the HR surface to the bulk itself. The system devoted to the aberration control in Advanced Virgo is the Thermal Compensation System (TCS) that is currently engaged to monitor and compensate wavefront distortions with an accuracy of the order of nanometers ensuring a duty cycle higher than 90%. In view of the increase of the input power up to 40 W planned for the observing run O4, the TCS actuation setup will have to be upgraded to face the higher circulating power and new control strategies will have to be implemented. An overview of the present TCS system installed on Advanced Virgo with a focus on the possible integrated and dynamical strategies combining multiple TCS actuators to improve its efficiency, is presented here.

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Introduction

Advanced Virgo is a power recycled Michelson interferometer with Fabry-Pérot (FP) cavity in the arms designed to measure the quadrupolar deformation induced by a gravitational wave passage [1, 2, 3] with a strain sensitivity ten times larger than the one of initial Virgo [4]. At the design working point, the input power is foreseen to reach 125 W, corresponding to ~ 1 MW stored in the FP cavities. In these conditions, even if the fractional absorption in the core optics is very low (less than 1 ppm in the high reflectivity coatings [5]), the power absorbed by the mirrors is in the range of hundreds of mW, thus making thermal effects no longer negligible [6]. The need of an adaptive correction of thermal effects during interferometer operation stimulated the development of a complex TCS composed by wavefront sensors and thermal actuators [7, 8]. The optical aberration sensors used in

the second generation of gravitational-wave detectors are the Hartmann Wavefront Sensors (HWS) that directly measure the change of a wavefront with respect to the reference one through a CCD collecting the wavefront distortions accumulated by an auxiliary probe beam. The thermal lensing is measured by the probe beam transmitted through the optic under test, while it is reflected back by the High Reflectivity (HR) surface of the mirrors, i.e. the surfaces facing the FP cavities, to measure the thermo-elastic deformation.

The mirror radii of curvature (RoCs) are tuned through the use of a Ring Heater (RH), an adaptive actuator encircling the optic and conceived to change its radius of curvature by inducing a thermo-elastic deformation equal but opposite to the thermal effect. The thermal lensing is compensated by CO₂ beams projected on the compensation plates (CPs), two auxiliary optics positioned in the power recycling cavity used to apply the thermal corrections.

During the commissioning phase for the preparation of O3 observing run, the TCS sensors and actuators have been characterized and now they are in full operation to keep the interferometer in the good working point for the science data acquisition. The current TCS configuration includes the CO₂ lasers to stabilize the power recycling cavity and the end test masses RHs switched on to increase the power circulating in the FP arms.

1 The Thermal Compensation System

The TCS [6, 7, 8] is conceived to tackle the aberration budget coming both from cold defects and from thermally driven effects. As a reference, a scheme of the TCS parts integrated in the Advanced Virgo layout is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Scheme of the Advanced Virgo TCS, superimposed on the optical layout of the detector. Blue and magenta beams (HWS-RC DET and HWS-RC INJ) represent the two HWS probe beams in transmission that allow to measure the thermal lensing in the North Input (NI) and West Input (WI) test masses, respectively. The HWSs devoted to the measurement of the thermo-elastic deformation are shown in violet. The red circles represent the RH actuators and the yellow rectangles the CO₂ laser benches.

1.1 Wavefront sensing

Since the Advanced Virgo power recycling cavity is marginally-stable, the compensation of the thermal lensing inside the ITM substrates is essential to avoid a degradation of the interferometer operation and to guarantee a good duty cycle. In fact, the aberrations due to the thermal effects generate High-Order-Modes (HOMs) which create offsets in the angular error signals making the global working point strongly affected and not reliable. Thus, two wavefront sensing setups have been designed to measure the aberration in transmission through the input optics. The phase distortion on the mirror is measured by a probe beam and then reported to a conjugate plane by using an afocal optical system. The afocal system allows the probe beam to match the size of sampled optics (tens of cm) and then to be reduced to the optimal size for the wavefront sensing. The choice of a SLED (Superluminescent Light Emitting Diode) source as probe beam was driven by the need of avoiding diffraction effects. HWSs [9] are employed to extract the phase information of the outgoing probe beam. The thermal lensing setup conceptual scheme is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Conceptual scheme of the probe beam propagation up to the input optics and reflected back to the HWS.

The front surface of the sensor is a plate containing an array of apertures that split the incoming beam into a series of rays. These rays, propagating normal to the local gradient of the wavefront, are incident on a CCD array placed at known distance L behind the plate and form a spot pattern on the CCD. The resulting image is digitized, recorded and the position of the i -th spot, x_i^1 , is determined by a centroiding algorithm with sub-pixel accuracy [9]. The displacement of the centroid of each spot x_i^1 , relative to some reference x_i^0 , provides a direct measurement of the local gradient of the incident wavefront. The complete data set of all spot measurements yields the gradient field of the wavefront:

$$\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial(x_i^1 - x_i^0)}{L}. \quad (1)$$

It can be shown [10] that the phase RoC seen by a differential sensor is proportional to the RoC on its conjugate plane through the inverse square of optical magnification M_{opt} :

$$RoC_{HWS} = \frac{RoC_{conj}}{M_{opt}^2}. \quad (2)$$

In the differential mode of operation, HWS shows an impressive accuracy. An RMS noise floor lower than 2 nm has been measured by the HWSs installed in Advanced Virgo (Figure 3).

Figure 3: RMS noise floor measured by the HWSs installed in Advanced Virgo power recycling cavity.

One of the main limits to the accuracy of HWS is the thermal deformation of the Hartmann plate, induced by environmental temperature variations, that can significantly affect the measurement. The spurious curvature measured by the HWS due to the thermal defocus of the HWS plate can be evaluated as [10]:

$$C = \alpha_{inv} \frac{\Delta T_{plate}}{L}, \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha_{inv} = 1.2 \times 10^{-6}$ 1/K is the expansion coefficient of the Invar, an alloy composed by nickel and iron, used to make the plate, ΔT_{plate} is the temperature variation of the plate and $L = 10$ mm is the distance between the HWS plate and the CCD.

The tests performed on the table top experiment TeTis (Testing the effects of TCS integrated strategies), developed in the INFN Virgo laboratory of the University of Rome Tor Vergata [10], showed a very good agreement between the expected and measured curvature values 4.

Figure 4: Comparison between the measured data (black curve) and the curvature values expected from calculations (yellow curve). The red and purple lines correspond to the curvature behaviours considering 10% of uncertainty in the value of the Invar expansion coefficient in the Equation 3 .

In order to minimize this contribution, a temperature stabilization system able to control the temperature at the level of 0.01 K [11] has been implemented on the HWS.

The environmental temperature change also generates a thermal defocus in the afocal telescopes introducing another spurious contribution to the curvature. In this case, adding a secondary probe beam at a different wavelength, propagating through the afocal system but reflected back before entering the measured path, would allow the subtraction of thermal defocus effects. This solution, called two-colour system, will be experimentally investigated as a possible near future upgrade.

1.2 Actuation: ring heaters

A radiative element providing touchless tuning of the radius of curvature of core optics by means of local heating has been adopted in the design of state-of-art gravitational wave detectors [12, 13]. The heaters are made of two emitting PYREX rings surrounded by a polished copper shield. The rings are heated by Joule effect, using a helicoidal wrapping of a NiCr flat wire. All the RH materials are suitable for Ultra-High-Vacuum operation. The coil currents of the two heating rings are counter-propagating. In this way the coupling of the stray magnetic field along the test mass axis with actuation magnets is made negligible. At full power, the Advanced Virgo RH is able to decrease the mirror RoC by 100 m over a cold value of 1.5 km. According to thermo-mechanical simulations, the achieved actuation gain is $\frac{dRoC}{dP} = -0.93$ m/W with a high degree of sphericity. The transient behaviour of ΔRoC shows a typical overshoot, approaching the regime value in about 15 h. A spherical thermal lens inside the mirror is also created, with a gain $\frac{d(f^{-1})}{dP} = 8 \times 10^{-6}$ m⁻¹ W⁻¹.

1.3 Actuation: CO₂ laser projectors

CO₂ lasers are used to compensate the thermal lensing generated by the main laser beam in the input test mass substrates. They emit radiation at $\lambda = 10.6 \mu\text{m}$ that is completely absorbed by the fused silica. The CO₂ source has a maximum power of 50 W and the power is distributed among three different actuation lines.

A Gaussian intensity spot with the same beam size of the main interferometer beam on the input test masses ($\sim 50 \text{ mm}$ [6]) has been implemented to keep unchanged the thermal status of the detector when a cavity unlock happens, allowing a fast recovery of the working point. This actuator is so called Central Heating (CH).

The thermal lens due to coating absorption in the input masses can be compensated using an optimized axi-symmetric heat distribution on CPs that is obtained as a sum of two ring-shaped intensity patterns [6]. Each ring is produced using an axicon lens, then the two rings are superimposed on an object plane. Hence, the object is imaged onto the CP by a suitable lens. This arrangement is called Double Axicon System (DAS) and allows the power in the two rings to be separately controlled. The conceptual scheme can be shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Conceptual scheme of the DAS obtained as a sum of two ring-shaped intensity patterns. The DAS image is the real DAS projected in Advanced Virgo.

To tackle the residual, asymmetric distortion, the TCS baseline solution is the so called Scanning System (SS) [14]. SS consists in a Gaussian spot that is scanned along a raster pattern on the CP. Fast steering (up to several kHz step frequency) is provided by galvanometric mirrors. The power delivered on each spot is controlled through an AOM. The desired asymmetric intensity pattern is then obtained as the sum of all the spots: the slow thermal diffusion in silica performs a temporal low-pass filtering of the pattern repetitions. The optimal heating for a given distortion is obtained through an iterative approach that uses FEM simulations [6]. Then, the intensity for each spot is computed via a pseudo-inverse matrix approach.

2 Thermal Compensation system during O3 science run

In the first part of O3 science run (O3a) with an input power equal to 20 W the role of the compensation of the optical aberrations appeared fundamental to avoid a degradation of the ITF operation and to guarantee a good duty cycle. Thermal aberrations scatter out the power from the TEM00 mode

causing a loss of S/N ratio of the signal used to control the ITF and, at the same time, the HOMs prevented a robust interferometer longitudinal control worsening the alignment performances. Thus, the CO₂ DAS actuation is currently in use to guarantee a sufficient S/N ratio to keep the ITF in the good working point. As it can be seen in Figure 6-left, after ITF reaches the optimum working point (time equal to 400 s in the figure), the signal use to control some of the longitudinal and angular degrees of freedom of the ITF starts to decrease causing the loss of the working point after about half an hour. The downward trend is instead corrected by shining the DAS on both CPs (Figure 6-right).

Figure 6: Left: behavior of the signal used to control the ITF at the bright port with DAS OFF. Right: behavior of the same signal after engaging the DAS.

During the commissioning phase, some criticalities, related to the thermal transient phenomena which lengthen the achievement of the good working point, have been identified. In particular, it has been observed that when ITF is not in operation and cools down, the procedure to allow the ITF to reach again the working point becomes more difficult. Thus, the CO₂ CH actuator has been commissioned in order to reproduce the same thermal lens generated by the main laser keeping unchanged the thermal state of the ITF when it is not in operation.

During O3a the RH actuators have also been switched on to tune the RoC of the end mirrors in order to change the power mode content circulating in the FP arms maximizing the intra-cavity power. In Figure 7 the power transmitted by the end mirrors of both FP cavities with the end mirror RHs ON and OFF are compared: the intra-cavity power increased by 15 % using the RH.

Figure 7: Power transmitted by the end mirrors of North arm and West arm FP cavities when the RHs around the end mirrors are ON and OFF.

The scanning of the RH powers needed to find the optimal ones was a very slow procedure since, as previously mentioned, the RH thermal constant is very long (about 15 hr). Thus, the investigation of new approaches in order to reduce the time needed to reach the steady state is started and will be discussed in the next Section. Another critical issue observed during the commissioning period is related to the switching on of the input test masses RHs. In fact, the thermal lens induced by these actuators causes an immediate degradation of the power recycling cavity stability causing the unlock of the cavity itself. To avoid this unwanted effect, the CO₂ CH actuator could be used to compensate the diverging lens induced by RH. In view of the power increase foreseen for the next observing run, it is essential to optimize the TCS single actuator operation and the combined action of multiple actuators to minimize the transient thermal phenomena reducing the ITF downtime.

3 Thermal Compensation system future improvements

Among the actuators, the RH has the longest actuation time. So, in order to ease the use of the RH, a new strategy has been devised, with the goal to reach a steady state curvature in about 1 hour. Since the increments in temperature of the mirror are small in the RH actuation range, the radiative emission can be considered approximately linear. Therefore, the system composed by the RH and the mirror can be assumed linear (the RH response, in terms of curvature or thermal lens, scales linearly with the applied power). Thus, once the mirror thermal lens (or thermo-elastic deformation) response to a step input (1 W to the RH) is known by simulations, the Laplace transform can be used to calculate the transfer function of the system as:

$$TF(s) = s \mathcal{L}(r_\theta), \quad (4)$$

being r_θ the response as a function of time. The transfer function is then used to design a time dependent input signal $P(t)$ (power to the RH) to get a fast response, requiring the regime condition be attained in ~ 1 hr. An example of the application of this actuation scheme for the AdV test masses is shown in Figure 8: by modulating the power applied to the RH (Figure 8-left), the steady state thermal lens value for 1 W applied can be reached in 1 hr (Figure 8-right).

Figure 8: Left: Simulated modulation of the power applied to the RH in order to reach the steady state thermal lens value for 1 W applied in ~ 1 hr. Right: The simulated curvature behaviour of the mirror by applying 1 W to the RH (blue) compared to that simulated by applying the modulated power (red).

The RH actuation on the input mirror induces a thermal lensing in the ITM substrates that could spoil the control signals resonating in the power recycling cavity. In order to counterbalance the diverging lens induced by the RH, the central heating appears to be the suitable actuator, since it generates a lens of opposite sign. So, by calculating the transfer function, it is possible to modulate the power applied to the CH in order to compensate the opposite lens generated by the RH for each time step. An example is reported in Figure 9-right: the thermal lensing effect induced by 1 W applied to the RH is counterbalanced by modulating the CH power as shown in Figure 9-left.

Figure 9: Left: Simulated modulation of the power needed to the CH to compensate the thermal lens generated by the RH (1 W applied) for each time step. Right: The simulated thermal lensing curvature behaviour by applying 1 W to the RH (blue) and the simulated curvature values by modulating the CH power (red).

All these techniques will be tested in the Virgo Laboratory of the University of Rome Tor Vergata before to be implemented in Advanced Virgo for the O4 observing run.

Conclusions

The Thermal Compensation System for Advanced Virgo has been presented, describing the methods employed for the sensing and correction of wavefront distortion in the detector. The role of the TCS on the optimization of the interferometer global working point has been already observed during O3 and proved to be essential to avoid a degradation of the interferometer operation and to guarantee a good duty cycle. The path of Advanced Virgo toward its design sensitivity is strictly related to the increase of the input power and thus, to the efficiency of the thermal compensation system. In this framework, new strategies to improve the accuracy of the sensors are under investigation. The two color system has been proposed to decouple the curvature measured by the HWS due to the power absorption in the optic from the spurious one, due to the thermal defocus in the telescope bringing the information from the optic to the sensor. Moreover, an active temperature control on the HWS has been developed in order to reduce the spurious curvature due to the thermal expansion (or contraction) of the HWS plate. These upgrades will be installed in Advanced Virgo during the break between the observing runs O3 and O4.

During the commissioning phase some criticalities have been identified in particular related to the transient thermal phenomena which starts when the ITF cools down. To overcome this issue, the CO₂ central heating actuator is currently used to mimic the effect of the main laser.

The RHs actuators are now in operation to maximize the power circulating in the FP arms. The RH time constant is quite long requiring one day to scan each working point, thus, the modulation of the power applied to the RH has been proposed in order to reduce the time needed to reach the steady state. The combined action of multiple actuators is also under investigation, in particular the CO₂ CH represents the suitable actuator to counterbalance the diverging lens induced by the RH around the input test masses.

The combined action of multiple actuators and the enhancement of the sensor performances is fundamental to ensure the accuracy and the time versatility required to the TCS to cope with higher circulating power.

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